

Interview Scheme Outline

Authors' Additional Notes on the Interview Scheme

1. The interview scheme is presented here only with respect to the themes relevant to this study. The interview scheme also included two additional themes that were not directly relevant to the present study:
 - Positive and Motivating Aspects of Working in the Game Development Industry (Theme 4)
 - Flow Experiences in the Game Development Industry (Theme 5)
2. The interview scheme was developed incrementally throughout the data collection process.
3. The themes and questions were not always addressed in a strict order. Rather, the conversation was allowed to flow naturally, with emphasis placed on themes most relevant to the discussion at hand.
4. Clarifying and reflective questions were used where necessary to gather additional detail and to ensure the interviewer accurately understood the interviewee's intended meaning.

Start of the interview

At the start of each interview, the interviewers introduced themselves, emphasized the confidentiality and anonymity of participation, and provided an overview of the study's main themes. Additionally, interviewees were asked to complete a preliminary questionnaire collecting the following information: age, gender, nationality, level of education, employment status, job title, role in game development, work experience in game development, and work experience in software development (in general).

Theme 1: Working in the Game development industry (and Its Challenges)

This theme focused on the interviewees' work in the game development industry and their career history within it. Interviewees were asked to describe aspects such as their current role, length of experience in the industry, perceptions of the industry as a work environment, the game development process in their organization, the general nature of working in the industry, the types of challenges and stressful experiences they have faced, how they have attempted to cope with these challenges or stress, and whether they would like to see changes in the industry aimed at mitigating these challenges or stress.

Exemplary Questions:

- Could you tell us about your work and what you do?
- What kinds of games do you develop or work with?
- What is your role in the game development process?
- How would you describe your organization and the game development industry as a work environment?
- What kinds of challenges have you encountered when working in the game development industry?
- Have you experienced stress while working in the game development industry, and if so, why?
- How have you tried to alleviate or cope with the stress?

Theme 2: Technology Use

This theme focused on the interviewees' use of technology, particularly how it is integrated into their daily work. Interviewees were asked to describe aspects such as the types of technologies commonly used in the game development industry, the specific tools they personally use, how they use them, and the role technology plays in both their daily work tasks and broader work life.

Exemplary Questions:

- What types of technologies are commonly used in the game development industry?
- What technological tools do you use in your work?
- How would you describe the role of technology in your work?

Siitonen, V., Ritonummi, S., Salo, M., Koskelainen, T., & Pirkkalainen, H. (2025). Searching for Social Conditions Contributing to Technostress Emergence in Organizational Information Technology Use (Online replication package). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17049021>

- Which technologies are most important for your work?

Theme 3: Technology Use and Stress (Technostress)

This theme focused on the challenges and stress associated with technology use in the interviewees' work. Interviewees were asked to describe aspects such as the types of challenges they have encountered with technology, how and why technology use has caused stress in their work, and to provide detailed examples of stressful situations involving technology use in the game development industry and how they have attempted to cope with them.

Exemplary Questions:

- What types of challenges have you experienced related to technology use in your work in the game development industry?
- Have you experienced stress related to technology use, and if so, why?
- How or why did these stressful experiences emerge?
- Could you describe a specific stressful experience in as much detail as possible?
- How have you tried to alleviate or cope with this stress?

Concluding the Interview

To conclude the interview, interviewees were invited to share any additional thoughts or raise topics they felt had not been sufficiently covered. They were also encouraged to highlight anything they considered important or relevant to the themes discussed.

Exemplary Question:

- Is there anything you would like to add or mention that we haven't yet covered?